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ConcePTION

WP7 – Information and data governance, ethics, technology, data catalogue and quality support

D7.8 Database with reprotox data on platform

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Document History

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Abstract

Regulatory non-clinical safety testing of human pharmaceuticals typically requires embryo–fetal developmental toxicity (EFDT) testing in two species (one rodent and one non-rodent). This deliverable aimed to rank of Non-Clinical Rat and Rabbit Embryo-fetal Developmental Toxicity Data compared to maximum recommended human therapeutic dose. Data were obtained from a database of compounds that was established by CBG and RIVM, based on publicly available data. Out of the 58 compounds, 50 were classified as increased concern for human teratogenicity. This ranking based on pre-clinical data should be combined with drug utilization data (D7.17) to assess exposure risks and prioritization of RWE studies.

Introduction

The developmental toxicity of pharmaceuticals is typically evaluated through embryo-fetal developmental toxicity (EFDT) studies in two species: a rodent, commonly the rat, and a non-rodent, often the rabbit (ICH)ⁱ. These studies aim to identify potential risks to fetal development, including structural malformations, growth impairments, and functional deficits, which are critical for assessing the safety of pharmaceuticals for human use. Over the past three decades, numerous studies have compared rat and rabbit developmental toxicity data for the same pharmaceutical compounds. A comparative analysis of these studies offers valuable insights into which species is more sensitive for detecting developmental toxicity, whether single-species testing is sufficient, and if one species could be chosen as the default for initial testing. Given the standardization of animal study protocols, it is feasible to compare the sensitivity of rats and rabbits in identifying developmental toxicity, with systemic exposure kinetics serving as a basis for this comparisonⁱⁱ.

To enhance the understanding of developmental toxicity between these two species, the RIVM and CBG-MEB developed a comprehensive database containing EFDT data from both rats and rabbits. The results of these analyses are summarized in two key studies by Theunissen, Piersma, et al. which was the basis for the work conducted in ConcePTION.

The first study, titled "Comparison of rat and rabbit embryo-fetal developmental toxicity data for 379 pharmaceuticals: on the nature and severity of developmental effects", built and queried a database of 379 pharmaceutical compounds with EFDT studies (in both rat and rabbit animal models) conducted for marketed and non-marketed pharmaceuticals for their potential for adverse developmental and maternal outcomes, including EFDT incidence and the nature and severity of adverse findings. Manifestation of EFDT in either one or both species was demonstrated for 282 compounds (74%). EFDT was detected in only one species (rat or rabbit) in almost a third (31%, 118 compounds), with 58% (68 compounds) of rat studies and 42% (50 compounds) of rabbit studies identifying an EFDT signal. For 24 compounds (6%), fetal malformations were observed in one species (rat or rabbit) in the absence of any EFDT in the second species. In general, growth retardation, fetal variations, and malformations were more prominent in the rat, whereas embryo-fetal death was observed more often in the rabbit. According to the authors discordance across species may be attributed to factors such as maternal toxicity, study design differences, pharmacokinetic differences, and pharmacologic relevance of species. The analysis suggested that in general both species are equally sensitive on the basis of an overall EFDT LOAEL comparison, but selective EFDT toxicity in one species is not uncommon. Also, there appeared to be species differences in the prevalence of various EFDT manifestations (i.e. embryo-fetal death, growth retardation, and dysmorphogenesis) between rat and rabbit, suggesting that the use of both species has a higher probability of detecting developmental toxicants than either one aloneⁱⁱⁱ

The second study, "Comparing rat and rabbit embryo-fetal developmental toxicity data for 379 pharmaceuticals: on systemic dose and developmental effects", focuses on the relationship between systemic exposure and developmental outcomes. Species differences in developmental toxicity were analyzed using toxicokinetic parameters, specifically area under the curve (AUC) and maximum concentration (C_{max}) at the developmental lowest adverse effect level (dLOAEL). In 83% of cases (AUC, n = 283), dLOAELs in rats and rabbits were within the same order of magnitude (less than 10-fold difference). For 13.5% of compounds, the rabbit was more sensitive, while 3.5% showed greater sensitivity in rats based on AUC. Similarly, 12% of compounds were more sensitive in rabbits and 1.3% in rats when considering C_{max}. When evaluating human equivalent doses (HED), rats and rabbits showed equivalent sensitivity. The extent of embryo-fetal toxicity, in the presence of maternal toxicity, was similar between species, with comparable overall effect severity incidences in both rat and rabbit studies. No significant species differences were observed in embryo-fetal variations or systemic exposure LOAEL distributions within strains. Given the differences in developmental effects between

species for individual compounds, EFDT studies in two species provide added value compared to single-species studies^{iv}.

As part of the ConcePTION project a ranking was created with the aim to create a prioritization for pharmacoepidemiological studies.

Methods

We utilized publicly available non-clinical data from embryofetal development toxicity (EFDT) studies in rats (rodent) and rabbits (non-rodent) to prioritize compounds based on their potential to induce long-term effects in children following exposure during pregnancy. EFDT studies were selected based on their relevance to the assessment of teratogenicity and embryofetal lethality, as these compounds have been shown to often result in long-term effects in humans (e.g., valproate) (see figure 1). A list of 176 compounds that were licensed between 2004 and 2012 were obtained as well as a list of 22 known human teratogens^v. These compounds were screened for rabbit and rat data, and those with positivity for malformation and/or embryo-fetal death retained. Of these compound exposure margin data was searched.

Compounds were ranked by the following criteria:

- 1. Presence of Malformations and/or Embryofetal Lethality (MEFL):** The primary endpoint for each study was the identification of malformations or signs of embryofetal lethality.
- 2. Margin of Safety:** For each compound, the margin of safety was calculated as the ratio between the area under the curve (AUC) of the compound at the no observed adverse effect level (NOAEL) in animals and the AUC at the maximum recommended human dose (MRHD). This ratio provides a benchmark for comparing the relative safety of each compound across species. A higher ratio suggests a greater margin of safety, indicating less risk to human health.

- a. **AUC (Animal at NOAEL):** The AUC of the compound at the NOAEL in the selected animal species was derived from the EFDT studies in both rats and rabbits.
 - b. **AUC (Human at MRHD):** The human AUC at the MRHD was based on available clinical data.
3. **Further Ranking Based on Most Sensitive Species:** The final ranking of compounds took into account the species sensitivity, with additional prioritization given to those compounds exhibiting the lowest margin of safety in the most sensitive species. This was based on both MEFL outcomes and AUC-derived safety margins to identify compounds with the highest potential for adverse long-term effects in children.

Results

Table 1 shows the ranking of compounds for the rat studies. A total of 23 compounds had AUC ratios below 1 indicated increased concern, most of these compounds are for treatment of cancer. Other compounds are for osteoporosis, which may not occur in women of childbearing age. However, several compounds within increased concern relate to indications that may occur in childbearing age or pregnancy such as epilepsy, acne and inflammation. Within the orange classified compounds with increased concern, many more indications relate to conditions that could occur in pregnancy or in childbearing age.

Table 1: Ranking of compounds inducing MEFL in rat based on Rat AUC/Human AUC ratio

Ranking	Compound	Species	Malformation	Death	AUC NOAELrat/human	Indication	ATC code	Status
1	pralatrexate	Rat	0	1	0,00	Lymphoma, T-Cell	L01BA05	
2	cyclophosphamide (prodrug)	Rat	1	1	0,00	Treatment of malignant diseases	L01AA01	
3	Phosphoramidate mustard (active metabolite cyclophosphamide)	Rat	1	1	0,01	Treatment of malignant diseases	L01AA01	
4	sorafenib tosylate	Rat	1	1	0,02	Carcinoma, Hepatocellular, Carcinoma, Renal Cell	L01XE05	
5	Methotrexate	Rat	1	1	0,02	rheumatoid / juvenile idiopathic arthritis, psoriasis	L01BA01	
6	bazedoxifene	Rat	0	1	0,02	Osteoporosis, Postmenopausal	G03XC02	
7	ixabepilone	Rat	0	1	0,03	Advanced / metastatic breast cancer	L01DC04	With draw n
8	pazopanib	Rat	1	1	0,04	Renal cell carcinoma, soft tissue carcinoma	L01XE11	
9	valproic acid	Rat	1	0	0,06	Epilepsy, bipolar disorder, prevention of migraine	N03AG02	
10	strontium ranelate	Rat	1	0	0,06	Osteoporosis, Postmenopausal	M05BX03	
11	everolimus	Rat	0	1	0,10	Tuberous Sclerosis	L01XE10	
12	Dimethadione metabolite	Rat	1	1	0,13	Antiepileptic	N03AC02	
13	Acetylsalicylic acid	Rat	1	1	0,14	Stomatological preparation, Antithrombotic, Analgesic	A01AD05, B01Ac06, N02BA01	
14	vismodegib	Rat	1	0	0,17	Antineoplastic	L01XX43	
15	trimethadione	Rat	1	1	0,20	Antiepileptic	N03AC02	
16	naproxcinod	Rat	1	1	0,31	Anti-inflammatory and antirheumatic	M01AE18	With draw n
17	5-Fluorouracil	Rat	1	1	0,34	Antineoplastic	L01BC02	
18	All-trans-retinoic acid	Rat	1	0	0,47	Anti-acne, antineoplastic	D10Ad01, L01XX14, D10AD51	
19	dasatinib	Rat	1	1	0,48	Precursor Cell Lymphoblastic Leukemia-Lymphoma, Leukemia, Myelogenous, Chronic, BCR-ABL Positive	L01XE06	

20	13-cis-retinoic acid	Rat	1	1	0,64	Anti-acne	D10AD04	
21	Phenytoin	Rat	1	0	0,70	Antiepileptic	N03AB02	
22	Ibuprofen	Rat	1	0	0,71	Anti-inflammatory, Analgesic	M01AE01	
23	Nilotinib	Rat	1	1	0,84	Leukemia, Myelogenous, Chronic, BCR-ABL Positive	L01XE08	
24	telavancin	Rat	1	0	1,06	Antibacterial	J01XA03	
25	pirfenidone	Rat	1	0	1,54	Idiopathic Pulmonary Fibrosis	L04AX05	
26	gemifloxacin	Rat	1	0	1,77	Antibacterial	J01MA15	
27	Acitretin	Rat	1	0	1,83	Anti-psoriatic	D05BB02	
28	thalidomide	Rat	0	1	2,19	Immunosuppressant	L04AX02	
29	rotigotine transdermal patch	Rat	0	1	2,32	Restless Legs Syndrome, Parkinson Disease	N04BC09	
30	Carbamazepine	Rat	1	1	2,36	Antiepileptic	N03AF01	
31	Cytarabine	Rat	1	1	2,41	Antineoplastic	L01XY01	
32	Fluconazole	Rat	1	1	2,82	Anti-mycotic	J02AC01	
33	liraglutide	Rat	0	1	3,33	Diabetes Mellitus, Type 2	A10BJ02	
34	ambrisentan	Rat	1	1	3,69	Hypertension, Pulmonary	C02KX02	
35	topiramate	Rat	1	0	3,90	Antiepileptic	N03AX11	
36	Tigecycline	Rat	0	1	4,81	Bacterial Infections, Skin Diseases, Bacterial, Soft Tissue Infections	J01AA12	
37	Busulfan	Rat	1	0	5,10	Antineoplastic	L01AB01	
38	salicylate	Rat	1	1	5,75	Stomatological, Antithrombotic, Analgesic	A01AD05, B01Ac06, N02BA01	
39	dronedarone hydrochloride	Rat	1	1	6,90	Atrial Fibrillation	C01BD07	
40	Vildagliptin	Rat	0	1	10,47	Diabetes Mellitus, Type 2	A10BH02	
41	lumiracoxib	Rat	0	1	13,32	Anti-inflammatory, anti-rheumatic	M01AH06	
42	eplivanserin hemifumarate	Rat	0	1	13,33	NA	None	With draw n
43	voclosporin	Rat	0	1	14,05	Immunosuppressant	L04AD03	
44	tafamidis meglumine	Rat	0	1	21,91	Amyloidosis	N07XX08	
45	aclidinium bromide	Rat	0	1	23,61	Obstructive airway disease	R03BB07	
46	entecavir	Rat	1	1	26,70	Hepatitis B, Chronic	J05AF10	
47	Pomalidomide	Rat	1	1	85,32	Immunosuppressant	L04AX06	
48	dapagliflozin	Rat	1	1	1066,88	Diabetes Mellitus, Type 2, Diabetes Mellitus, Type 1	A10BK01	

Red text: no observed adverse effect level (NOAEL) not reached, used data from lowest observed adverse effect level (LOAEL) dose.

Table 2 provides information on the ranking and classification in rabbits. A total of 39 compounds were labelled red or orange indicating increased risk for human teratogenic potential. Many of these are indicated for treatment of cancer, but several are for indications that may occur in childbearing age/pregnancy such as epilepsy, acne, inflammation.

Table 2: Ranking of compounds inducing MEFL in rabbit based on Rabbit AUC/Human AUC ratio

Rank	Compound	Species	Malformation	Death	AUC NOAELrabbit/human			
1	Phosphoramidate mustard (active metabolite cyclophosphamide)	Rabbit	1	1	0,0008	L01AA01	Treatment of malignant diseases	
2	ixabepilone	Rabbit	0	1	0,0034	L01DC04	Advanced / metastatic breast cancer	Withdrawn at MAA
3	pralatrexate	Rabbit	0	1	0,0048	L01BA05	Lymphoma, T-Cell	
4	cyclophosphamide (prodrug)	Rabbit	1	1	0,03	L01AA01	Treatment of malignant diseases	
5	pazopanib	Rabbit	0	1	0,04	L01XE11	Renal cell carcinoma, soft tissue carcinoma	

6	lapatinib	Rabbit	0	1	0,04	L01XE07	Antineoplastic	
7	sorafenib tosylate	Rabbit	1	1	0,07	L01XE05	Carcinoma, Hepatocellular, Carcinoma, Renal Cell	
8	5-Fluorouracil	Rabbit	1	0	0,10	L01BC02	Antineoplastic	
9	gemifloxacin	Rabbit	0	1	0,11	J01MA15	Antibacterial	
10	naproxcinod	Rabbit	0	1	0,15	M01AE18	Anti-inflammatory and antirheumatic	Withdrawn at MAA
11	valproic acid	Rabbit	1	1	0,17	N03AG02	Epilepsy, bipolar disorder, prevention of migraine	
12	Nilotinib	Rabbit	0	1	0,17	L01XE08	Leukemia, Myelogenous, Chronic, BCR-ABL Positive	
13	liraglutide	Rabbit	1	1	0,18	A10BJ02	Diabetes Mellitus, Type 2	
14	Methotrexate	Rabbit	1	1	0,19	L01BA01	rheumatoid / juvenile idiopathic arthritis, psoriasis	
15	dronedaron hydrochloride	Rabbit	0	1	0,22	C01BD07	Atrial Fibrillation	
16	bazedoxifene	Rabbit	0	1	0,24	G03XC02	Osteoporosis, Postmenopausal	
17	topiramate	Rabbit	0	1	0,29	N03AX11	Antiepileptic	
18	everolimus	Rabbit	0	1	0,30	L01XE10	Tuberous Sclerosis	
19	All-trans-retinoic acid	Rabbit	1	1	0,39	D10Ad01, L01XX14, D10AD51	Anti-acne, antineoplastic	
20	Tigecycline	Rabbit	0	1	0,55	J01AA12	Bacterial Infections, Skin Diseases, Bacterial, Soft Tissue Infections	
21	Phenytoin	Rabbit	1	0	0,66	N03AB02	Antiepileptic	
22	Febuxostat	Rabbit	0	1	0,85	M04AA03	Anti-gout	
23	thalidomide	Rabbit	1	1	0,85	L04AX02	Immunosuppressant	
24	micalfungin	Rabbit	1	0	1,02	J02AX05	Anti-mycotic	
25	Pomalidomide	Rabbit	1	0	1,04	L04AX06	Immunosuppressant	
26	Carbamazepine	Rabbit	0	1	1,15	N03AF01	Antiepileptic	
27	erlotinib	Rabbit	0	1	1,28	L01XE03	Antineoplastic	
28	telavancin	Rabbit	1	0	1,32	J01XA03	Antibacterial	
29	13-cis-retinoic acid	Rabbit	1	1	1,62	D10AD04	Anti-acne	
30	strontium ranelate	Rabbit	1	0	1,63	M05BX03	Osteoporosis, Postmenopausal	
31	ambrisentan	Rabbit	1	1	1,76	C02KX02	Hypertension, Pulmonary	
32	Rimonabant	Rabbit	1	1	1,85	NA	NA	Withdrawn from registry
33	eplivanserin hemifumarate	Rabbit	1	1	1,89	None	NA	Withdrawn at MAA
34	retapamulin	Rabbit	0	1	2,67	D06AX13	Antibiotic	
35	tafamidis meglumine	Rabbit	1	1	3,16	N07XX08	Amyloidosis	
36	lumiracoxib	Rabbit	0	1	3,39	M01AH06	Anti-inflammatory, anti-rheumatic	
37	Gadofosveset Trisodium	Rabbit	1	1	3,70	NA	Diagnostic	Withdrawn from registry
38	Fluconazole	Rabbit	0	1	3,86	J02AC01	Anti-mycotic	
39	tenofovir disoproxil	Rabbit	0	1	5,87	J05AF07	Anti-viral	
40	paliperidone	Rabbit	0	1	22,47	N05AX13	Anti-psychotic	
41	rilpivirine	Rabbit	1	0	53,68	J05AG05	Anti-viral	
42	entecavir	Rabbit	0	1	202,11	J05AF10	Hepatitis B, Chronic	
43	eprodissate disodium	Rabbit	0	1	785,08	NA	NA	Withdrawn at MAA

Red text: no observed adverse effect level (NOAEL) not reached, used data from lowest observed adverse effect level (LOAEL) dose

Table 3 combines the data from rat and rabbit to give an overall ranking based on the lowest AUC ratio, a total of 30 compounds were labelled red and 20 orange, indicating of increased concern.

Table 3: Ranking of both rat and rabbit data based on lowest animal/ human AUC ratio

Ranking	Compound	Rat	Rabbit	Rat Malformation	Rat Death	Rabbit Malformation	Rabbit Death	AUC NOAELrat/human	AUC NOAELrabbit/human	Lowest AUC ratio
1	pralatrexate	Rat	Rabbit	0	1	0	1	0,00	0,00	0,00
2	Phosphoramidate mustard	Rat	Rabbit	1	1	1	1	0,01	0,00	0,00
3	ixabepilone	Rat	Rabbit	0	1	0	1	0,03	0,00	0,00
4	cyclophosphamide (prodrug)	Rat	Rabbit	1	1	1	1	0,00	0,03	0,00
5	sorafenib tosylate	Rat	Rabbit	1	1	1	1	0,02	0,07	0,02
6	Methotrexate	Rat	Rabbit	1	1	1	1	0,02	0,19	0,02
7	bazedoxifene	Rat	Rabbit	0	1	0	1	0,02	0,24	0,02
8	pazopanib	Rat	Rabbit	1	1	0	1	0,04	0,04	0,04
9	lapatinib		Rabbit	#N/B	#N/B	0	1	NA	0,04	0,04
10	valproic acid	Rat	Rabbit	1	0	1	1	0,06	0,17	0,06
11	strontium ranelate	Rat	Rabbit	1	0	1	0	0,06	1,63	0,06
12	5-Fluorouracil	Rat	Rabbit	1	1	1	0	0,34	0,10	0,10
13	everolimus	Rat	Rabbit	0	1	0	1	0,10	0,30	0,10
14	gemfloxacin	Rat	Rabbit	1	0	0	1	1,77	0,11	0,11
15	Dimethadione metabolite	Rat		1	1	#N/B	#N/B	0,13	NA	0,13
16	Acetylsalicylic acid	Rat		1	1	#N/B	#N/B	0,14	NA	0,14
17	naproxen	Rat	Rabbit	1	1	0	1	0,31	0,15	0,15
18	vismodegib	Rat		1	0	#N/B	#N/B	0,17	NA	0,17
19	Nilotinib	Rat	Rabbit	1	1	0	1	0,84	0,17	0,17
20	liraglutide	Rat	Rabbit	0	1	1	1	3,33	0,18	0,18
21	trimethadione	Rat		1	1	#N/B	#N/B	0,20	NA	0,20
22	dronedaron hydrochloride	Rat	Rabbit	1	1	0	1	6,90	0,22	0,22
23	topiramate	Rat	Rabbit	1	0	0	1	3,90	0,29	0,29
24	All-trans-retinoic acid	Rat	Rabbit	1	0	1	1	0,47	0,39	0,39
25	dasatinib	Rat		1	1	#N/B	#N/B	0,48	NA	0,48
26	Tigecycline	Rat	Rabbit	0	1	0	1	4,81	0,55	0,55
27	13-cis-retinoic acid	Rat	Rabbit	1	1	1	1	0,64	1,62	0,64
28	Phenytoin	Rat	Rabbit	1	0	1	0	0,70	0,66	0,66
29	Ibuprofen	Rat		1	0	#N/B	#N/B	0,71	NA	0,71
30	thalidomide	Rat	Rabbit	0	1	1	1	2,19	0,85	0,85
31	micafungin		Rabbit	#N/B	#N/B	1	0	NA	1,02	1,02
32	Pomalidomide	Rat	Rabbit	1	1	1	0	85,32	1,04	1,04
33	telavancin	Rat	Rabbit	1	0	1	0	1,06	1,32	1,06
34	Carbamazepine	Rat	Rabbit	1	1	0	1	2,36	1,15	1,15
35	erlotinib		Rabbit	#N/B	#N/B	0	1	NA	1,28	1,28
36	pirfenidone	Rat		1	0	#N/B	#N/B	1,54	NA	1,54
37	ambrisentan	Rat	Rabbit	1	1	1	1	3,69	1,76	1,76
38	Acitretin	Rat		1	0	#N/B	#N/B	1,83	NA	1,83
39	Rimonabant		Rabbit	#N/B	#N/B	1	1	NA	1,85	1,85
40	eplivanserin hemifumarate	Rat	Rabbit	0	1	1	1	13,33	1,89	1,89
41	rotigotine transdermal patch	Rat		0	1	#N/B	#N/B	2,32	NA	2,32
42	Cytarabine	Rat		1	1	#N/B	#N/B	2,41	NA	2,41
43	retapamulin		Rabbit	#N/B	#N/B	0	1	NA	2,67	2,67
44	Fluconazole	Rat	Rabbit	1	1	0	1	2,82	3,86	2,82
45	tafamidis meglumine	Rat	Rabbit	0	1	1	1	21,91	3,16	3,16
46	lumiracoxib	Rat	Rabbit	0	1	0	1	13,32	3,39	3,39
47	Gadofosveset Trisodium		Rabbit	#N/B	#N/B	1	1	NA	3,70	3,70
48	Busulfan	Rat		1	0	#N/B	#N/B	5,10	NA	5,10
49	salicylate	Rat		1	1	#N/B	#N/B	5,75	NA	5,75
50	tenofovir disoproxil		Rabbit	#N/B	#N/B	0	1	NA	5,87	5,87
51	Vildagliptin	Rat		0	1	#N/B	#N/B	10,47	NA	10,47
52	voclosporin	Rat		0	1	#N/B	#N/B	14,05	NA	14,05
53	paliperidone		Rabbit	#N/B	#N/B	0	1	NA	22,47	22,47
54	acridinium bromide	Rat		0	1	#N/B	#N/B	23,61	NA	23,61
55	entecavir	Rat	Rabbit	1	1	0	1	26,70	202,11	26,70
56	rilpivirine		Rabbit	#N/B	#N/B	1	0	NA	53,68	53,68

57	eprodisate disodium		Rabbit	#N/B	#N/B	0	1	NA	785,08	785,08
58	dapagliflozin	Rat		1	1	#N/B	#N/B	1066,88	NA	1066,88

Discussion

This study aimed to rank pharmaceutical compounds that are known teratogens (see Andrews) or were licensed in the EU between 2004 and 2012) with publicly available information on EFDT studies, as assembled in a database by CBG and RIVM. Ranking was done to allow for prioritization of increased teratogenic risk based on animal studies. A total of 58 compounds had either rat or rabbit studies and could be compared. 50 out of these 58 compounds had an increased concern for teratogenic potential in humans. Most compounds are for indications that will be rare in women of childbearing age, such as cancer, but some compounds are for indications that may occur in childbearing age such as epilepsy, acne, infection and inflammation.

This ranking is based studies are on animal studies, and the relevance for RWE studies should be inspected, using drug utilization studies, allowing to see which of the compounds are used in women of childbearing age and during pregnancy. If they are used it would be crucial to monitor neonatal and long-term outcomes.

Conclusion

This study provides a prioritized ranking of 58 pharmaceutical compounds with known or suspected teratogenic potential, based on available EFDT (Embryo-Fetal Development Toxicity) data from animal studies. Given that the ranking is based on preclinical data, there is a critical need to complement these findings RWE through drug utilization studies.

ⁱ ICH. 2005. ICH harmonised tripartite guideline: detection of toxicity of reproduction for medicinal products and toxicity to male fertility S5(R2). Available from: <http://www.ich.org/products/guidelines/safety/safety-single/article/detection-of-toxicity-to-reproduction-for-medicinal-products-toxicity-to-male-fertility.html>

ⁱⁱ Theunissen, P. T., Beken, S., Beyer, B., Breslin, W. J., Cappon, G. D., Chen, C. L., ... Piersma, A. H. (2016). Comparing rat and rabbit embryo-fetal developmental toxicity data for 379 pharmaceuticals: on systemic dose and developmental effects. *Critical Reviews in Toxicology*, 47(5), 409–421. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10408444.2016.1224808>

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